

Capturing and Sustaining Competitive and Strategic Advantage by Creating Favorable Online Customer Shopping Experiences

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Abstract

The evolution of the internet, increased literacy, Smartphone addictions, data availability at affordable prices, busy schedule of working people, changing scenario of the socioeconomic conditions worldwide especially after the Pandemic has boosted up Online Business. In the present era online shopping has become a part of almost everyone's life. Favorable or Positive customer experiences result in increased customer engagement, customer satisfaction, repurchase intention, customer retention, eWOM, customer equity and brand equity. Hence online customers shopping experience (OCSE) can act as an important differentiator and attract new customers and retain the existing ones. OCSE helps in creating value to the customers and thus proves to be one of the important sources of competitive advantage. Meeting the fast and continuous changing needs and expectations of online customers has become inevitable for online retailers. Enhancing shopping experiences and creating value for online customers with every new transaction can sustain this competitive advantage. The research paper identifies how differentiation, cost advantage and focus strategies can create value and favorable online customers shopping experiences for the customers and competitive and strategic advantage for online retailers.

Keywords: *Online Customers Shopping Experience (OCSE), Differentiation, Cost Advantage, Focus, Competitive Advantage and Strategic Advantage.*

Introduction

A swift change is being witnessed in the field of online marketing. Internet usage has expanded rapidly in India, and the pandemic has increased the appeal of online shopping. Online marketing has great potential to help E-Retailers grow and succeed. Despite facing challenges and strong competition in the e-tailing sector, e-retailers are capitalizing on the opportunities. Creating a valuable overall customer experience is key to building customer satisfaction and Loyalty amongst target audience. Favorable customer experience, acts as a tool for getting, keeping and growing customers. Today it is inevitable for online marketers to analyze and understand the changing needs, wants and desires of customers and thereby promote customer value and loyalty through creating favorable customer experiences.

Favorable online customers shopping experiences can then become a pathway through which competitive advantage and strategic advantage can be achieved by the company. The study is relevant in the present scenario and aims to provide solutions like differentiation, cost and focus strategies to online Marketers that help to create value and favorable customer experiences and there by capture and sustain competitive advantage and strategic advantage for itself.

Review of Literature

Online shopping is more sustainable than offline shopping (**Bharati Makhijani, 2023**). Customer experience has steadily become the most important source of retailers' long-term competitive advantage via difference (**Farooq Ahmad et al., 2022**). Retailers need to continuously improve customer experience in different shopping situations to maintain long term sustainable customer satisfaction and achieve sustainability (**Xue-Liang Pei,et al., 2020**).

The factors influencing online shopping behavior have a prominent role in the growth and long term competitiveness of E-Commerce Companies (**Svatosova, V. 2020**). Improving the e-service quality (system design, intelligent fulfillment, security assurance, and interactive service) has a strong positive effect on stimulating customer engagement behavior (**Wenfang Fan, Bingjia Shao and Xiaohua Dong 2022**), Customer satisfaction significantly and directly affects customer loyalty (**Thabang Excellent Mofokeng ,et al.,2021**). Online consumer satisfaction acts as mediator between online service quality and future purchase intentions(**Kalia et al.,2016**).

The review of literature finds that numerous studies are conducted on various aspects of consumer attitude towards online shopping, Factors influencing online consumers buying behavior, Women consumer buying behavior towards online shopping, consumer's perception on online shopping. Several comparative studies of customer behavior and attitude towards online and offline shopping has also added to the literature. However, little is available in the literature about the impact of favorable online customers shopping experience on competitive advantage and in turn the strategic advantage of the company.

The review of the literature conducted for the current study makes it clear that there is further scope to study how favorable OCSE acts as a source of competitive advantage of the company. Businesses can leverage on the three important strategies cost advantage, differentiation and focus to create value for the customers and thereby capture and sustain competitive advantage and strategic advantage for itself.

Objectives of the study:

1. To identify the factors influencing Customer Value and Online Customers Shopping Experiences
2. To explain the relationship between favorable Online Customers Shopping Experiences and competitive advantage and strategic advantage of the company

Theoretical Framework

The Research explains how online retailers can use Michael Porters tools such as Differentiation, Cost advantage and Focus strategies in creating Value and favorable Online Customers Shopping Experiences which in turn gains Competitive and Strategic advantage for the Company.

Differentiation Strategy creates value and favorable OCSE

The Differentiation strategy emerges as a powerful approach that enables companies to offer distinctive products, services, or experiences that resonate with customers (**Jerab. Et al., (2023)**). Companies can create superior customer value through differentiation because today's customers don't want to be a part of the crowd. Online Retailers can use strategies such as offering Exclusive Product lines, AI driven product recommendations, augmented reality, product try ons, live chats, customer support system, hassle free returns, easy

exchanges, value based pricing, subscription models, loyalty programs, virtual assistants etc to create favorable online experiences for customers.

Differentiation Advantages: Positive OCSE through differentiation converts satisfied customers into delighted customers, delighted customers into loyal customers who then partner with the company in co-creating value. To have a vast delighted and loyal customer base is a strong differentiation factor for the company.

Focus (Niche) Strategy creates value and favorable OCSE

Online retailers can create value by tailoring their services to specific target groups and meet the specific requirements of customers. Companies can capitalize the niche marketing advantages. Favorable OCSE is established when e-retailers maintain good relationship with customers and focus on them, there by promoting strong Customer Relationship Management. Thus companies also can reap CRM advantages when they are much focused. Focused strategies may include specializing in specific category such as baby products, sports products, handicrafts, organic products etc. Focusing can also be based on demographics, Focus may be upon sustainability and ethics. Online retailers can adopt targeted marketing using AI and data analytics.

Focus Advantages: Understanding that group's unique needs whether they are based on demographics, values, or interests is crucial. Building a devoted clientele and encouraging word-of-mouth advertising can be achieved by focusing product offers, branding, and marketing initiatives on that niche. Thus online retailers can use focus strategy in creating value and superior experiences.

Cost Advantage strategy creates value and favorable OCSE

Cost advantage refers to a situation where companies offer at lesser prices than its competitors but still maintain its profitability. By optimizing supply chains, streamlining operations, achieving economies of scale, maintaining quality, and implementing value-based pricing, organizations can position themselves as low-cost producers while offering valuable products or services to customers (**Jerab, Daoud & Mabrouk, Tarek.2023**). Technological adoptions such as data driven decisions and cloud technologies can reduce IT related costs. Targeted Advertising, Search Engine Optimization, shipping, packing, and mobile optimization, global outsourcing, automated warehouses and use of robots are some other ways of reducing costs.

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Cost Advantages: Cost leadership helps in increasing customer base and market share. This strategy not only creates value for customers but also captures Customer Life Time Value. Customer experiences are positive when they pay less than expected.

Combining Differentiation, Cost advantage, and focus strategies, create value and favorable OCSE

Applying Porter's generic strategies allows firms to successfully achieve their essential purposes, which are to survive, be profitable, and increase market share (Islami et al., 2020). Online retailers can adopt this hybrid strategy and create distinct value for a specific segment at prices even after maintaining profitability.

Hybrid Strategies Creates Value and Favorable OCSE: A superior value and favorable experiences can be created combining cost advantage, focus and differentiation when companies deliver low cost, high value and tailored products.

Favorable OCSE captures and Sustains competitive advantage and in turn strategic advantage for online retailers

Favorable online customer Experience is a route to capture and sustain competitive advantage which ultimately leads to strategic advantage for online retailers. Online Retailers that put efforts in creating favorable experiences enjoy market leadership, long term profitability, loyal customer base, brand equity, Customer Life Time Value etc. Online customers with positive experiences engage more time in the website resulting in cross selling and up selling by the E-retailers. Satisfied and Delighted customers always have repurchase intentions and will also recommend their friends and relatives about the websites and products. Marketers can use favorable OCSE weapon to drive out their competitors and achieve competitive advantage. To capture competitive advantage might be difficult for companies but to sustain that competitive advantage is even difficult. So meeting the changing needs, wants and expectations of the present day customers is inevitable for every online marketer to not only create competitive advantage but also strategic advantage.

Model Representing Online Customers Shopping Experience as a Tool to Capture and Sustain Competitive Advantage

Research Implications

In the digital era, satisfied customers play a crucial role in not only achieving success but also in driving sustainable growth and prosperity of the business. To satisfy the present day customers is not at all easy. Customers today are more demanding and less forgiving. It takes fraction of seconds for them to switch to another website. With the passage of time the concept of loyal customers is diminishing. They expect Companies to create value for them in every transaction. In such situation creating favorable online shopping experiences becomes quite essential. Online retailers need to continuously analyze the changing needs and wants of customers and put best efforts to meet them. Satisfying customers is not enough but delighting them is the need of the hour. Online retailers must concentrate on value creating activities for the customers and in turn customers will create value for the company through providing Customer Life Time Value (CLV). Satisfied and loyal customers are an asset to the company. Online Retailers can adopt Michael Porters strategies such as differentiation, Cost leadership and Focus to capture Competitive advantage and turn

it to strategic advantage. Advancements in technology, Wave of Artificial Intelligence has made E-retailing more profitable and at the same time challenging. To retain the existing customers and attract many more customers' online retailers need to go for value chain analysis, SWOT analysis, Porters five forces model analysis and identify where it stands, in the market, what value it creates for its customers and engage in keeping its customers engaged with it.

Limitations and Future Research Directions

- The present study is much generalized and the same study can be extended with reference to aspecific product or industry.
- The research can be supported with empirical evidence by the future researchers

Conclusion

Customer experience encompasses all product consumed, all interactions with the service team, and all engagements with a product. Customer experience is now a significant distinguishing factor in every industry. Investing in Customer experiences is important for organizations that value their reputation and aim to have happy, delighted and loyal customers. Effective customer experience not only aids in keeping current clients, but it also allows organizations to use their image to draw in new customers. Online retailers whose prime motto is creating value and favorable customers shopping experiences automatically capture Competitive Advantage and Strategic Advantage

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